

ENSURING INVESTMENT ACTIVITY IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION OF PRODUCTION.

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Abstract

in this article, in the conditions of modernization of production in our country, ensuring investment activity, increasing the competitiveness of products produced on the basis of modern techniques and technologies, and strengthening the country's export potential through foreign investments, reforming, liberalizing and modernizing our economy, diversifying its structural structure a series of analytical data about making.

Key words

investments, product competitiveness, export potential, foreign investments, security, profitability, capitalization, liquidity, investment environment, investment activity, investment policy.

It is known from world practice that any country cannot develop without attracting foreign investments to its economy. Modernization of economic sectors and their intensive development, renewal of the main funds of sectors, elimination of social problems of the country, increase of competitiveness of products produced on the basis of modern techniques and technologies, and strengthening of the country's export potential are ensured through foreign investments.

In addition to safety, profitability, capitalization and liquidity, a unique and important feature of foreign investments is the pursuit of specific goals. The economy that attracts their attention also strives to achieve its goals. These goals can be tasks such as efficiency, production growth, market penetration. Therefore, mutual interests, trust relations, taking into account the conditions of penetration are the basis for the transfer of investments from one country to another.

Today, the comprehensively justified and well-thought-out policy of reforming, liberalizing and modernizing our country, first of all, our economy, and diversifying its structural structure, is a strong barrier that protects us from the negative effects of crises and other threats. created a strong and reliable means of protection.

Further deepening of structural reforms in the economy, revitalization of

investment activities of enterprises, wide attraction of foreign investments, first of all direct foreign investments and their effective use, modernization of production, technical and technological rearmament, new work a large amount of funds are being allocated from the republican budget in order to ensure the stable and rapid development of our national economy on this basis.

The main goal of investment-innovation activities in the economy is to create optimal conditions for the development and acceleration of the use of innovative opportunities based on investments. also, it is necessary to take into account the nature and forms of organizational and economic mechanisms when making investments in various sectors of the economy. The effectiveness of investment-innovation activity is ensured in the investment complex system, which includes leasing, insurance, research institutes, information-consulting offices, banks and other organizations.

State support for the development and promotion of investment-innovative activity

In Uzbekistan, the system of receiving capital for production is improving year by year. Currently, laws and decisions are being developed based on the rules of modern international economic relations regarding foreign investments, as well as the infrastructures of foreign investments are being created. All the factors mentioned above are important for a foreign investor.

Indeed, in recent years, the scope of measures aimed at increasing the volume of investments has been significantly increased both legally and practically.

Especially as a result of active investment policy, positive growth in the dynamics of investment flow is observed in our republic.

For the development of the economy and social sphere of the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-March 2023, 56.6 trillion sums of investments in fixed assets were disbursed from all sources of financing, which is 103.1% compared to the corresponding period last year.¹¹³

Dynamics of the volume of investments in fixed assets for January-March, trillion soums

If you look at the growth rate of investment over the past five years, it becomes obvious that until 2019 it increased and reached 141.8%, in 2020 there was stability - 104.6%, in 2021 it dropped to 97.8% , and then continued to grow and to date amounted to 103.1%.

Dynamics of growth rates of investments in fixed assets for January-March, in %

Currently, one of the most important tasks in the field of economic development is to create favorable conditions for attracting foreign investments to the economy of our country, to introduce practical mechanisms for their legal protection, and to further improve the investment environment.

The investment policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a leader among the CIS countries in providing more favorable conditions for attracting foreign investments, establishing a practical mechanism for reliable legal protection of foreign investments, and on this basis, further improving the investment environment in the country.

¹¹³ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/4.Investments%20and%20construction.pdf

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Acceptable industry-specific documents also include:

- creation of the most favorable investment environment for foreign investors making direct investments in the development of high-tech productions;
- to encourage the attraction of foreign investments for the implementation of projects on modernization of production, technical and technological updating;
- elimination of various bureaucratic pitfalls and obstacles in working with foreign investors;
- to prevent illegal interference by state and control agencies in the activities of enterprises with foreign investments.

"Investment policy strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025" was prepared by the Ministry of Economy and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of international experience, analysis of trends and problems in the development of investment processes of the republic's economy, its sectors and regions.

Table 1

Indicators	2018 y	2019-2025 y	2025 y
GDP, trillion soums	407,5	106 %	1298,9
Share of investments in GDP	30,5%		37,5
Foreign investments and loans, billion dollars		30,8	11,0
Decentralized investments, billion soums		1002,5	
Investments in fixed capital	103,9	110,8	

The goal of the investment policy until 2025 is to increase the competitiveness and balance of the economy, develop production and export potential, develop regions and increase the welfare of the population.

The main tasks of the strategy are defined in three main directions: improving the investment environment, expanding domestic investment sources and improving the efficiency of investment sources, implementing effective measures and developing new approaches to attract foreign investments. Until 2025, the main

sources of investments will be direct investments, including public-private partnerships, public investments and corporate securities investments. It is planned to absorb more than 1,002.5 billion soums of decentralized investments within the framework of new and promising investment projects in 2019-2025. Also, about 30 percent is financed from the enterprises' own funds.

The economic efficiency of attracting and using investments in industry in the context of active investment policy is described and analyzed. Uzbekistan's investment policy, in particular, indicators of the economic efficiency of their use, are analyzed in a narrow and broad framework. The "Investment Policy Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025" of the Republic of Uzbekistan specifies the requirements for all types of investments. Proposals on the prospects for the development of investment policy in Uzbekistan are presented.

At the same time, the world practice and experience shows that it is no longer possible to solve the problems that hinder business investment and innovation activity by simple means, that is, by giving incentives or publishing new declarative norms. Liberalization of business activities is required to activate private investments. It is necessary to work diligently to identify and overcome obstacles that prevent the development of certain sectors, constant dialogue with business. In this regard, active work is being carried out in the following directions.

First of all, in order to maintain high and stable rates of economic growth, it is necessary to create a stable and competitive model of the country's economy, in which a large part of the banking system's assets are in the hands of private investors.

Secondly, in order to increase investment attractiveness and ensure the rapid growth of infrastructure investments, which are one of the main factors of sustainable economic growth, investment activities are being actively promoted through the development of public-private partnerships and project financing tools. .

Thirdly, relations between investors and the state are being optimized in order to completely eliminate bureaucratic obstacles and restrictions in the implementation of investment projects through digitization and remote provision of public services. In order to ensure maximum transparency and prevent corruption, the quality of organization of work with appeals and requests of foreign investors is improving.

Fourth, there is a reduction in transaction costs that lead to the flow of labor and capital from the legitimate sectors of the economy to the underground economy.

Fifth, an investment policy strategy focused on the most promising sectors of Uzbekistan, which can become a point of technological progress and create a basis for the development of the country's production capacity in the next 20-30 years, is being developed.

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REFERENCES:

1. Liesbeth Colen, Miet Maertens and Jo Swinnen. Foreign direct investment as an engine for economic growth and human development: A review of the arguments and empirical evidence. <https://www>.
2. Mihaela Peres, Waqar Ameer & Helian Xu (2018) The impact of institutional quality on foreign direct investment inflows: evidence for developed and developing countries, Economic Research-Ekonomiska Istraživanja, <https://doi.org/>
3. Andrianov V.D. Rossiya: ekonomicheskii i investitsionnyi potentsial. – M.: OAO «Izdatelstvo «Ekonomika», 1999. – 662 s.
4. Charaeva M.V. Finansovoe upravlenie realnymi investitsionnymi organizatsiyami: uchebnoe posobie / M.V. Charaeva. Moskva: Alfa-M, 2014. 240 s.
5. Uskovao T.V. Rol investitsiy v obespechenii ustoychivogo ekonomicheskogo rosta. Ekonomicheskie i sotsialnye peremennyye: fakty, tendentsii, prognoz 6 (30) 2013. S. 45-59.
6. Prusak M.M. Regionalnaya strategiya: investitsii v ekonomiku // Finansy. 2001. -№ 1. - S. 6-8.
7. Karimov N.G'. Iqtisodiy integratsiyalashuv sharoitida investitsiya faoliyatini moliyalashtirishning bozor mexanizmlarini joriy etish masalalari. – T.: Fan va texnologiya, 2007. – 240 b.

8. Nodirxanov U.S. Приятные иностранные investitsii v Uzbekistane: опыт проблемы, перспективы роста. - Т.: "G'an va texnologiya",2011. 184 b.
9. Rajabova M. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY FUTURE //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). - 2021. - Т. 8. - №. 8.
10. Rajabova M. WAYS TO ATTRACT FOREIGN INVESTMENT IN THE REGIONAL ECONOMY //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). - 2023. - Т. 36. - №. 36.
11. www.mineconomy.uz (Iqtisodiyot vazirligi);
12. www.mf.uz (Moliya vazirligi);
13. www.mfer.uz (Tashqi iqtisodiy aloqalar, investitsiyalar va savdo vazirligi);
14. www.stat.uz (Davlat statistika qo`mitasi);
15. www.lex.uz; (Qonun hujjatlari ma`lumotlari milliy bazasi);
16. www.cbu.uz (Markaziy bank);
17. www.ufrd.uz (O`zbekiston Tiklanish va taraqqiyot jamg'armasi)
18. www.mift.uz (O`zbekiston Respublikasi Investitsiyalar va tashqi savdo vazirligi)